

Review

Review on Water and Energy Integration in Process Industry: Water-Heat Nexus

Miguel Castro Oliveira ^{1,2,*}

¹ Low Carbon and Resource Efficiency, R&Di, Instituto de Soldadura e Qualidade, 4415-491 Grijó, Portugal; mciten@isq.pt

² Centro Recursos Naturais e Ambiente (CERENA), Departamento de Engenharia Química, Instituto Superior Técnico, Universidade de Lisboa, Avenida Rovisco Pais 1, 1049-001 Lisboa, Portugal; henrimatos@tecnico.ulisboa.pt

* Correspondence: dmoliveira@isq.pt; Tel.: +351-22-747-1950

Abstract: The improvement of water and energy use is an important concern in the scope of improving the overall performance of industrial process plants. The investment in energy efficiency comprehended by the most recent sustainability policies may prove to be an effective response to the fall of energy intensity rates associated with the economic crisis brought by the COVID-19 pandemic. The improvement in water efficiency may also prove to be a potential approach due to its interdependencies to energy use, whose exploitation comprises part of the study of the water-energy nexus. Waste heat recovery and water reclamation practices have been exploited to improve water and energy efficiency. A specific method designated “Combined Water and Energy Integration” has been applied to water recycling as both an additional water source and a heat recovery source in a set of water-using processes. In scientific and industrial domains, there is still a need for integrated approaches of water-using and combustion-based processes for overall water and energy efficiency improvements in industrial plants. In this work, an innovative approach for a simultaneous improvement of water and energy use is proposed based on process integration and system retrofitting principles. This proposal is based on the delineation of two innovative concepts: Water and Energy Integration Systems (WEIS) and Water-Heat Nexus (WHN). A review on existing technologies for waste heat recovery, thermal energy storage and heat-driven wastewater treatment is performed, following a conceptualisation design.

Keywords: heat recovery; thermal energy storage; wastewater treatment; Water and Energy Integration Systems; Water-Heat Nexus

Citation: Castro Oliveira, M.; Iten, M.; Matos, H.A. Review on Water and Energy Integration in Process Industry: Water-Heat Nexus.

Sustainability **2022**, *14*, 7954. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14137954>

Academic Editor: Sergio Nardini

Received: 12 May 2022

Accepted: 20 June 2022

Published: 29 June 2022

Publisher’s Note: MDPI stays neutral with regard to jurisdictional claims in published maps and institutional affiliations.

Copyright: © 2022 by the authors. Licensee MDPI, Basel, Switzerland. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

1. Introduction

Water and energy efficiency are prominent concerns for industry and the improvement of the use of both of these resources is prominent in sustainability policies established by each country worldwide [1]. The adoption and planning of water and energy management strategies is essential to securing an efficient and sustainable operation of plants [2]. Considering the inevitable use of such resources in industries, water and energy use have obligatory interdependencies. Such interdependencies are encompassed in the concept of the water-energy nexus [3–6]. The improvement of energy efficiency in industries has been a subject of study by several authors (namely regarding the identification and analysis of improvement measures [7–10], their application into industrial processes factories [11] and the optimization of single equipment [12]). Within the scope of energy efficiency improvement, the authors of the present study have assessed potential water efficiency improvements, namely measures which simultaneously improve water and energy use [13], through simulation models [14].

Water efficiency and energy efficiency are concepts that have been gradually introduced in the sustainability policies adopted by each country in the world. In the European

Union, targets for an efficient water and energy use were respectively established in the 2009 Water Framework Directive [15] and the 2012 Energy Efficiency Directive [16]. The most relevant objectives of the EU regarding sustainability have been established in the most recent 2030 Climate and Energy Framework (up to a 40% reduction in GHG emissions from 1990 levels, 32% share for renewable energy and 32.5% energy efficiency improvement) [17]. Furthermore, the European Green Deal was introduced as a roadmap for the promotion of circular economy, biodiversity restoration and pollution mitigation [18].

At the level of engineering studies, process integration (PI) research has emerged on the scope of the study of water and energy efficiency, with a methodology based on the analysis and assessment of several processes existing in plants and all potential interdependencies [19]. The implementation of Water and Energy Integration mandatorily involves a new planning of the overall operation of a plant, namely in respect to the recirculation of plant streams containing reusable water and energy [20]. Overall, such implementations require the installation of several technologies to promote water and waste heat recirculation in a perspective of system retrofitting [21].

This work presents two innovative concepts: Water and Energy Integration Systems (WEIS) and Water-Heat Nexus (WHN). These concepts are established through a review on the implementation of Water and Energy Integration in the process industry, namely through waste heat recovery, thermal energy storage and heat-driven wastewater treatment technologies. This work is part of ongoing research involving all aspects associated with the implementation of heat recovery, water treatment and recirculation and eco-efficiency promotion practices in the process industry [22–26].

2. Strategic Framework

The principle of progress towards industrial sustainability is based on the reduction in resource consumption and the environmental impacts associated with the waste produced in plants—mostly water, electricity, fuels and process raw materials [27]. In practice, the promotion of industrial sustainability is achieved by improvement measures which optimise water and energy use [11,28], the application of renewable energy resources [29] and the application of waste-to-energy technologies [30]. The concept of a circular economy has been emerging on the scope to transform waste into potential by-products, promoting reuse, recovery and recycling, in which the life cycles of the production chains are optimised [31]. Within the limit, the application of several measures converges on the reuse of resources (either material or energy) within the same industrial site.

2.1. EU Energy System Integration Strategy

The scope of this work is driven by EU Energy System Integration Strategy. This strategy originated from a combination of the European Green Deal [18] and the 2050 long-term strategy [32]. The definitions of the guiding principles of each pillar of this strategy and their correlations to this work are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Framework of water and energy contextualization based on EEIS.

Pillar	Definition of the Guiding Principles	Contextualization of the Work
1st Pillar Energy Efficiency and Circular Economy Nexus	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Energy efficiency first principle (giving priority to energy demand-side solutions in relation to energy supply-side ones, if more cost-effective) Waste heat recovery (WHR) from industrial sites at the centre of intra-plant energy efficiency improvement and the functioning of district heating and cooling networks (promotion of WHR practices in a wider perspective and the surpassing of existing barriers) Wastewater-to-energy (production of biofuels) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Focus on heat recovery and water valorisation (either as feed water, waste heat streams or through further valorisation in waste-to-energy) Recirculation of these streams allows the conceptualization of systems encompassing industrial processes which are circular in nature (resources inevitably produce wastes as by-products which are in turn recirculated as additional resources)

Table 1. Cont.

Pillar	Definition of the Guiding Principles	Contextualization of the Work
2nd Pillar Renewable-Based Electrification	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Compensation of growing electricity demand through use of renewable energy resources as primary energy forms • Electrification of industrial processes • Implementation of energy storage technologies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Electricity-producing heat recovery-based thermodynamic cycles, which are also included within the scope of this work
3rd Pillar Alternative Low-Carbon Fuels	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promotion of the use of green hydrogen in sectors with more difficult decarbonisation • Promotion of carbon capture and storage (CCS) and carbon capture and use (CCU) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The application of waste-to-energy to the sludge from wastewater treatment units may result in the production of renewable biofuels (through anaerobic digestion) and hydrogen (through electrolysis)

2.2. The Water-Heat Nexus (WHN) General Concept

In this work, a new concept of the Water-Heat Nexus (WHN) is introduced, which is based on a specific application of the water-energy nexus. It primarily consists of the analysis of the thermal energy supply and demand requirements of water systems which may be fulfilled by waste heat stream recirculation. Secondly, it consists of the use of considered wastes from water systems as valorised energy inputs in combustion-based processes. Much of the understanding of this concept is related to the analysis of the waste streams generated in a plant. Firstly, it is of note that this waste may not only be considered as material waste (such as the one present in wastewater [33]), but also as thermal energy that is wasted in processes, such as combustion (waste heat) [34]. Heat recovery systems consist of the application of energy management principles to plan the installation of several technologies. It is based on the recirculation of streams with an associated waste heat potential so as to obtain savings in fuel or electricity consumption [35,36]. The recirculation of water streams has a similar principle to the one of heat recovery, in which the water stream at the outlet of a certain process is recirculated in order to produce savings on freshwater consumption [37]. In the case of the planning of a system containing several water-using processes, it is often necessary (although not obligatory in all industrial cases) to treat wastewater streams for further recirculation [38–65]. Two types of streams result from wastewater treatment units. One of these types is treated water streams, which may be recirculated to produce savings in freshwater use [66] (this work uses water recirculation as a term to include both water recycling to the process of origin and water reuse from one process to another [67]). Another type is sludge streams, which in turn may be valorised through the implementation of wastewater-to-energy technologies [68]. The general interpretation of the WHN paradigm is pictorially represented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. General interpretation of Water-Heat Nexus (WHN).

3. Water and Energy Integration Technologies and System Retrofitting

The understanding of the application of Water and Energy Integration in Process Industry involves the analysis of the existing literature in Process Integration (PI) concepts and methodologies for the purpose of water and energy resource valorisation. In this work, process integration principles are set to be implemented for the purpose of system retrofitting of the existing industrial sites, which involve the installation of several technologies, for instance:

- Waste heat recovery [21,36,69] (including thermal energy storage [70]);
- Heat-driven wastewater treatment [71].

Table 2 presents a summary of the progress on Water and Energy Integration in the industrial sector.

Table 2. Progress on Water and Energy Integration at the industry level.

Aspect	Progress	Ref.
Overview of Process Integration	<p>Framework of process integration within the improvement of the use of utilities in industry and the involvement of numerical methods, including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use of several mathematical programming methods (including multi-objective programming); • Directions of the implementation of process integration; • Attainment of general results on water savings, energy savings and reduction in environmental impacts. 	[72–85]
Pinch Technology for Energy Efficiency Improvement	<p>Pinch analysis-based heat integration in industry, including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assembling of heat exchanger networks (HEN) in a plant; • Application of pinch technology to improve the operation of industrial processes and systems (for instance, ORC and Kalina cycle); • Simultaneous application of pinch and exergy analysis methods; • Implementation of algorithms for the assembling of energy management scenarios. 	[86–105]
Water Minimisation and Recirculation	<p>Strategies for the minimisation of freshwater consumption and reduction in water footprint, through:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The application of water pinch analysis (WPA) and water cascade analysis (WCA) methods; • The study of water management strategies; • The study of the reduction in wastewater discharge. 	[67,81,106–113]
Combined Water and Energy Integration	<p>Research on the simultaneous application of Water and Energy Integration within a water network, considering:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Simultaneous application of water and energy pinch; • Application of the concept of water-energy nexus from a process-based perspective. 	[54,114–117]

From the analysis of Table 2, it is observed that process integration in respect to heat recovery and water recirculation has been successfully developed through numerical models for further industrial implementations. Research in this field has also accounted for the requirements of related areas, such as energy management and water management. The existing methodology of Combined Water and Energy Integration has been shown to be effective for the minimization of the use of freshwater and hot/cold utilities in a water system with a variable number of water-using processes. This corresponds to the approach of the Water-Heat Nexus concept. However, it considers in its analysis water streams as the only streams to be recirculated and as a single type of process (in this case, a water network). Therefore, the integration of the aforementioned technologies is relevant in the scope to expand the applicability of this approach.

3.1. Heat Recovery Technologies (HR)

Waste heat recovery (WHR) technologies encompassing improved combustion systems, heat exchangers and electricity generation systems have been studied by several

authors [118,119]. Within these, thermal energy storage (TES) technologies emerged to address the dynamic heat supply and demand levels in a plant. Such storage presents advantages, such as better capacity factors, avoidance of heat losses and reduced investment cost (in combination with cost-expensive components) [71,120,121], making up for the issues of standard WHR technologies, such as the significant distance between heat source and sink, the lack of identification of existing heat sinks, operation disturbances and overall economic viability. Table 3 presents a characterization of several WHR technologies applied from a multisectoral perspective.

Table 3. Characterization of HR Technologies and Strategies.

Technology	Characterization	Ref.
Heat Exchanging Units		
Air–Gas Heat Exchangers (Air Preheaters)	Commonly applied for waste heat from exhaust gases of combustion processes to an air stream, having different configurations (recuperator, regenerator, rotary regenerator and run-around coil units) [122] and designs (plate heat exchangers [123,124] and heat pipe heat exchangers, HPHEs [125–127]). The HPHEs are specific air preheaters applied with a higher heat transfer capability and a need for less heat transfer surface area for the same quantity of heat. They have over fuel savings of 10–30% and less than a two-year payback time.	[122–134]
Liquid–Gas Heat Exchangers (Economisers)	Applied for the heating of the liquid stream, such as a water stream at the inlet of a boiler or a steam boiler. They have different configurations (non-condensing, condensing, finned tube and coiled tubes). In some economisers, the liquid stream may be recycled for thermal energy efficiency improvement. They have a typical fuel savings of 5–10% at present and a payback time of less than two years.	[135–139]
Heat Recovery Steam Generators (HRSG)	Complex technologies commonly applied to generate steam for heating processes within a plant and the operation of thermodynamic cycles for electric energy generation. They are normally consist of an economiser (in which the liquid stream is preheated in order to attain the boiling point), an evaporator (in which the saturated liquid is converted into gas) and a superheater (in which the vapour is overheated beyond its saturation point). They have an overall plant efficiency of 85–90% and an electricity generation system efficiency of 75–85%.	[140,141]
Thermodynamic Cycles		
Organic Rankine Cycle (ORC)	Similar to the Clausius–Rankine cycle (CRC), the working principle of this thermodynamic cycle consists of the capture of thermal energy from a heat source to evaporate an organic fluid. It is commonly implemented for low-grade WHR. The cycle generally consists of a turbine, an HRSG unit, a condenser and a pump (in many installations a regenerator is also installed to even further increase the system efficiency). With appropriate working fluid, it may lead to about a 6% increase in overall plant efficiency. The organic fluids R-12, R-123, R134a and R-717 have been demonstrated as suitable to produce high-efficiency systems and a considerable amount of electric energy. It has an associated typical payback time four to five years.	[142–149]
Kalina Cycle	A system similar to the CRC and ORC, using water-ammonia mixture as the working fluid and suitable for medium and high temperature applications. It is structurally similar to the Regenerative ORC, with an additional separator due to the high ammonia concentration of the turbine outlet gas stream (so as to assist the full condensation of the water-ammonia mixture). It presents an overall better WHR performance compared to the ORC, although it requires more maintenance. It has been assessed as having a minimum payback time of 5.8 years.	[150–155]
Supercritical CO ₂ Brayton Cycle (SCBC)	A system with a similar arrangement to a common Brayton cycle, using CO ₂ at a supercritical state as the working fluid. It has several advantages: a higher thermal efficiency, operation at a lower pressure across the system and a reduction in number of stages in the turbine. The heat extraction capability may be limited due to the heat transfer in the heater being processed at a low temperature range close to the maximum cycle temperature. It has been assessed as having a payback time range between eight and twelve years.	[156–159]

Table 3. Cont.

Technology	Characterization	Ref.
	Thermal Energy Storage	
Liquid Thermal Tank	A sensible TES technology based on the heating of a liquid continuum within a tank. It may be a part of systems with several configurations, with different material streams being used as heat source streams (in addition to solar thermal collectors and boiler units), with a generic configuration being presented in Figure 2a. Water (working temperature of 0–100 °C), thermal oils (working temperature of 0–400 °C), molten salts (working temperature of 150–565 °C) or sodium (working temperature of 100–882 °C) may be used as the liquid media. It has been assessed to have an average payback time of 14 years.	[70,160–164]
Phase Change Material (PCM) Heat Exchanger	A latent TES technology consisting of a heat exchanger operating in a transient mode. A specific application of this technology includes the preheating of combustion air at the inlet of a combustion-based process, using an exhaust gas stream as the heat source, as presented in Figure 2b. The transportation of the exhaust gas stream to the PCM–TES unit functions as the charging phase (in which the PCM phase in turn is almost completely melted) and the transportation of the air stream functions as the discharging phase (in which the PCM phase in turn is again solidified by releasing the latent heat). Common latent materials include: molten salts [165,166], metal alloys [167,168], eutectic inorganic [169] and organics [170–172]. It has been assessed to have a potential of 28.6–66.2% total energy savings and a payback time of 7.5–14.5 years.	[122,165–200]

Figure 2. Representations of (a) liquid thermal tank, (b) application of a PCM heat exchanger for air preheating (adapted from [200]).

3.2. Heat-Driven Wastewater Treatment Technologies (HDWTT)

A specific set of wastewater treatment technologies (WTT) which use the supply of thermal energy as the driving force are designated as heat-driven wastewater treatment technologies [71,201,202]. These may be framed within the overall conceptualization of Water and Energy Integration by analysing the potential for a determinate waste heat stream (e.g., exhaust gases [203]) to serve as the heat source for the operation of these units. In Table 4, several heat-driven wastewater treatment technologies are characterized.

Table 4. Characterization of WWT Technologies.

Technology	Description	Ref.
Multi-Effect Distillation (MED)	<p>An HDWWT technology with several operational advantages including: the use of low-temperature operational levels, the production of high-quality treated water, high thermal performance, the use of low pumping power, the requirement of minimum water pre-treatment and the requirement for minimum labour. Its limitations include: level of investment (highly expensive technology), considerable susceptibility to corrosion and existence of relatively low recovery ratio. A conventional MED unit may be divided into three sections: (i) first effect section (in which the heat source is a hot liquid); (ii) the second-to-last effects section (in which the heat source is the vapour stream produced in the immediately previous step for each particular effect); (iii) the condenser section (which condensates the last effect outlet vapour stream through heat transfer with the cold inlet saline water stream). It has been assessed to have a payback time of four to sixteen years. The overall process is represented in Figure 3a.</p>	[71,201,204–206]
Multi-Stage Flash Distillation (MSFD)	<p>An HDWWT technology with an operation principal similar to MED, with the following advantages: higher resistance against scaling compared to MED, large capacity for freshwater production, independence from the salinity of feed water, operational and maintenance simplicity, low performance degradation, production of high quality freshwater and potential for combination with other processes. It has disadvantages, including: the level of investment (high investment technology), requirement for high-level technical knowledge, highly thermal energy-intensive process (high operational temperatures) and low recovery ratio. It has been assessed to have an average of 3.3 years payback time. The overall process is represented in Figure 3b.</p>	[21,207–212]
Membrane Distillation (MD)	<p>An HDWWT technology that presents advantages in relation to conventional distillation technologies: low energy requirements, non-dependability from concentration polarization and lack of limit in feed water concentration. Its disadvantages include: investment cost (high investment cost associated to MD module) and possibility of membrane wetting in the case of the presence of surfactant and amphiphilic contaminants. It has been assessed to have a payback time between six and fourteen years. The temperature gradient within the MD module may be generated by a heat recovery system: single-loop as represented in Figure 3c (in which the heat source is directly connected to the membrane) or two-loop as represented in Figure 3d (in which a heat exchanger is implemented and also commonly a TES unit for transient mode systems). The MD module may have the following configurations: direct contact membrane distillation (DCMD); vacuum membrane distillation (VMD); air gap membrane distillation (AGMD); and sweeping gas membrane distillation (SGMD).</p>	[213–217]

Figure 3. Flowsheet representations of (a) Multi-effect distillation (MED), (b) Multi-stage flash distillation (MSFD), (c) single-loop Membrane Distillation (MD), (d) two-loop Membrane Distillation (MD) (adapted from [212,213]).

4. Water and Energy Integration Systems (WEIS) for Process Industry

Heat recovery and water recirculation principles result from the conceptualization of systems encompassing a set of recirculated streams from one process to several other processes. This study proposes a concept that goes beyond conventional ways of thinking, such as open-loop and linear economy-modelled systems (in which water and energy recirculation is mere or non-existing). In contrast, the soon-to-be conceptualized systems are closed-loop and circular economy-modelled. The most generalist conceptualization of such systems and its comparison with linear economy-based systems are represented in Figure 4.

Figure 4. General scheme for (a) a linear economy-based industrial installation consisting of a water system and a thermal process system and (b) a refurbished circular economy-based overall system consisting of a water system and a thermal process system.

Such industrial systems are associated with several designations in the literature:

- Heat exchanger networks (HEN) (for heat exchanger installation-based heat recovery) [105];
- Near-zero liquid discharge (NZLD) (for water systems with significantly decreased wastewater discharge owing to water treatment and recirculation) [218–220];
- Water–energy networks (WEN) and water-allocation and heat-exchanger networks (WAHEN) (for water systems in which previously discharged water streams are recirculated to simultaneously decrease the use of freshwater and hot and cold utilities) [45].

This work introduces and conceptualizes a new type of systems, designated as Water and Energy Integration Systems (WEIS). WEIS include all conceptualized superstructures encompassing a set of water-using processes and thermal processes and also the application of several technologies and strategies. WEIS consist of thermal processes (making up part of the constituent thermal processes system) and a set of water-using processes (making up part of the constituent water system). Within the conceptualization of WEIS, several technologies may be implemented that overall promote:

- Water recirculation simultaneously as a heat recovery source (hot utility and cold utility savings) and as an additional water source (freshwater savings) [50,53,64];
- Waste heat stream recirculation to thermal processes (fuel savings);
- Waste heat stream recirculation to the heaters of the water system (hot utility savings);
- Waste heat stream recirculation to the heat-driven wastewater treatment units [201];
- Use of the sludge resulting from wastewater treatment as an additional energy source (fuel savings).

Figure 5 represents the general rationale behind the concept of WEIS, with schematics of a water treatment and recirculation network (a set of water-using processes) and a heat recovery system (a set of thermal processes).

Figure 5. Flowsheet for (a) water allocation and heat exchanger networks (WAHEN) in which unit operations to be target of Water-Heat Nexus type analysis are signalled in red (adapted from [39]) and (b) heat recovery system constituted by four combustion-based thermal processes (general concept adapted from [28]).

The two systems represented in Figure 5 are conceptualized to consider all the potential recirculation within water-using processes and combustion-based thermal processes, respectively. The overall WEIS concept, however, requires further adaptation for the interdependencies between the water recirculation network (Figure 5a) and the heat recovery network (Figure 5b). Such analysis is relevant to further conceptualize these systems and also for the newly coined concept of the Water-Heat Nexus (WHN). This analysis involves identifying the unit operations for the water recirculation network, which requires thermal energy inputs—corresponding to the red spots in Figure 5a, namely:

- Heating spots (total waste heat from thermal processes that may be allocated for savings in hot utilities);
- Wastewater treatments units (particularly in the heat-driven ones, wastewater treatment requiring minimum energy input).

The analysis of thermal energy supply and demand requirements associated to each of the water networks points corresponds to the concept of the Water-Heat Nexus (WHN). This is a specific implementation that investigates the use of waste heat streams to be supplied as thermal energy inputs in another system for the promotion of water recirculation. In the general scheme represented in Figure 5, this paradigm corresponds to an amplification of the *Industrial Processes* part, in which the interdependencies of specific processes (categorised as water-using processes or thermal processes) are exploited.

4.1. Mass and Enthalpy Balances of a WEIS

The implementation of WEIS models relies on the definitions of mass and enthalpy balance equations. It serves to ultimately assess the difference between the water and energy inputs in the baseline case (with no implemented measures) and in the improved case (with implemented measures). Table 5 presents a general delineation of the mass and enthalpy balances that describe the phenomena occurring in a WEIS.

Table 5. General delineation of balance equations describing Water and Energy Integration Systems.

Process/ System	Balance	Equation		
Thermal Process	Mass Balance	$M_{Fuel} + M_{C.Air} = M_{ExGas}$	(1)	
	Enthalpy Balance	$M_{Fuel} \cdot (h_{Fuel} + LHV) + M_{C.Air} \cdot h_{C.Air} = q_{useful} + M_{ExGas} \cdot h_{ExGas}$	(2)	
	Heat recovery equations	$q_{supply} = M_{Fuel_{initial}} \cdot LHV$	(3)	
		$q_{supply} = M_{Fuel} \cdot LHV + q_{additional}$	(4)	
Water-Using Process	Mass Balance	$M_{WP,in} + M_{cont.} = M_{WP,out}$	(5)	
	Enthalpy Balance	$M_{WP,in} \cdot h_{WP,in} = M_{WP,out} \cdot h_{WP,out}$	(6)	
Wastewater Treatment Unit	Mass Balance	$M_{WWT,in} = M_{WWT,out} + M_{sludge}$	(7)	
	Enthalpy Balance	$M_{WWT,in} \cdot h_{WWT,in} + q_{WWT} = M_{WWT,out} \cdot h_{WWT,out}$	(8)	
Water System	Heater	Mass Balance	$M_{Heater,in} = M_{Heater,out}$	(9)
		Enthalpy Balance	$M_{Heater,in} \cdot h_{Heater,in} + q_{HU} = M_{Heater,out} \cdot h_{Heater,out}$	(10)
	Cooler	Mass Balance	$M_{Cooler,in} = M_{Cooler,out}$	(11)
		Enthalpy Balance	$M_{Cooler,in} \cdot h_{Cooler,in} = M_{Cooler,out} \cdot h_{Cooler,out} + q_{CU}$	(12)
Recirculation Point (Splitting)	Mass Balance	$M_{water,in} = M_{water,out} + \sum_i M_{recir. water,i}$	(13)	
	Enthalpy Balance	$M_{water,in} \cdot h_{water,in} = M_{water,out} \cdot h_{water,out} + \sum_i M_{recir. water,i} \cdot h_{recir. water,i}$	(14)	

Table 5. Cont.

Process/ System	Balance	Equation
Recirculation Point (Joint)	Mass Balance	$M_{water,in} + \sum_i M_{recir. water,i} = M_{water,out}$ (15)
	Enthalpy Balance	$M_{water,in} \bullet h_{water,in} + \sum_i M_{recir. water,i} \bullet h_{recir. water,i}$ $= M_{water,out} \bullet h_{water,out}$ (16)

The sets of equations presented in Table 5 must be furtherly adapted to each reality specifically for the purpose of model development. For instance, the categories of thermal processes include a variety of equipment which includes other streams in addition to gas and material products (such as the material cooling fluid streams), and as such, the useful heat parcel (q_{useful}) varies for different processes.

4.2. Computational Tools for WEIS

The assessment of the implementation of WEIS in real-life plants may strongly benefit from the use of computational tools. As highly complex systems, computational tools are comprehensive, from a developmental level to further optimisation modelling. Table 6 presents a synthesis of models and methods of existing computational tools commonly used for the analysis of processes and phenomena involved in WEIS.

Table 6. Description of existing computational tools.

Type	Description	Ref.
Simulation Tools	Applicable for scenario analysis, sensitivity analysis and further API-based integration with optimisation models. The unit operations simulation models included in WEIS may be developed overall using existing software packages and modelling languages, such as Modelica [221–227], TRNSYS [228], ASPEN HYSYS [229–231], Apros [232], AMESim [233] and MATLAB/Simulink [234,235]. The technologies/measures being simulated include hot air recycling as combustion air, the implementation of heat exchangers for water/air preheating, organic Rankine cycles, multi-effect distillation units and PCM heat exchangers.	[23,221–235]
Optimisation Tools	Optimisation models for heat recovery/water recirculation systems overall are within the categories of mathematical programming (MP) and pinch analysis (PA) method applications. The PA method is a holistic perspective for the application of a systematic approach for the planning of industrial systems, although it suffers from the adoption of a steady-state perspective only and a high number of assumptions about fluid properties and temperature profiles [48,52,54,57,236–239]. MP methods may be formulated to require less assumptions, but are less systematic in nature, and include linear and non-linear programming (LP, NLP, MILP and MINLP) [39,40,42,43,46,47,51,55,56,59,62,65,240–245], multi-objective programming (MOP) [45,246–250] and dynamic programming (DP) [251–256]. These optimisation models have been prominently developed using the Modelica, Python and GAMS languages.	[22,36,37,39–45,48,49,51–57,59,61,62,236–257]

As may be verified from Table 6, several simulation and optimisation models conjointly achieve the aims of analysis and assessment of the technologies and phenomena involved in WEIS. In terms of component-level models, the existing models overall fulfil each type of required technology/phenomenon comprised the general concept of WEIS. The existing optimisation methodologies are also sufficient for the development of optimisation models for WEIS, considering both steady-state and dynamic perspectives. With the aim to assemble system-level models, the existing models and methodologies require adaption for the analysis of several levels of stream recirculation within WEIS and all the optimisation of involved costs (overall minimization of water costs, energy costs and investment costs).

5. Conclusions and Future Work

This work aimed to establish the concepts of Water and Energy Integration Systems (WEIS) and Water-Heat Nexus (WHN) by identifying and characterizing several technologies for waste heat recovery (WHR), thermal energy storage (TES) and heat-driven wastewater treatment (HDWWT). Such identification and characterization of technologies are the foundation of the understanding of all the potential interdependencies between water-using processes and thermal processes in an industrial site, which the aforementioned two concepts depend on.

In respect to the exploitation of existing heat recovery technologies (encompassing in this case both standard WHR and TES technologies):

- The existing WHR technologies fulfil the technical specifications for the conceptualized WEIS;
- The existing TES technologies are adequate within the conceptualization of the proposed WEIS, although it is still necessary to perform a further study with respect to the applications of these in specific cases (e.g., within the scope of the recirculation of heat streams from thermal process systems to water systems encompassing an energy storage component).

In respect to the exploitation of existing heat-driven wastewater treatment technologies:

- The existing technologies are adequate in the scope of the developed concept, although it is still necessary to research the specifications of these in terms of the characterizations of contaminant removal (namely specific types of contaminants and whether single- or multi-contaminant removal).

In respect to the implementation of WEIS and the concept of Water-Heat Nexus in general:

- The conceptualized WEIS concept is overall in accordance with the aims of the EU Energy System Integration, namely in terms of the practical implementation of circular economy principles;
- The conceptualized general WEIS scenario (as represented in Figure 5) may still have to be adapted in order to consider all potential recirculation of waste heat streams (namely as the heat source in the heaters and heat-driven wastewater treatment units of the water allocation and heat exchanger network), and furthermore, according to the requirements of different case studies;
- The existing computational tools (comprising simulation and optimisation models) are overall sufficient for the development of WEIS models, although further adaptations at the level of stream recirculation (connections between unit operations through material streams) must be performed.

A specific set of technologies that apply sorption and reaction phenomena designated as thermochemical technologies may be proposed for implementation to enhance the maturity of WEIS as viable market options. These comprise both energy storage and wastewater-to-energy technologies; their adequacy for WEIS may be explored in a future works.

Author Contributions: M.C.O., M.I. and H.A.M. performed the literature review; M.C.O. wrote the paper; M.I. and H.A.M. revised the paper. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This work was supported by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programmes under grant agreement "No. 810764" and through CERENA under grant UIDB/04028/2020_UIDP/04028/2020.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement: Not applicable.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Nomenclature

Abbreviations

CCS	Carbon capture and storage
CCU	Carbon capture and use
CRC	Clausius–Rankine cycle
DP	Dynamic programming
EU	European Union
GHG	Greenhouse gases
HDWWT	Heat-driven wastewater treatment
HEN	Heat exchanger network
HR	Heat recovery
HRSG	Heat recovery steam generator
LP	Linear programming
MD	Membrane distillation
MED	Multi-effect distillation
MILP	Mixed-integer linear programming
MINLP	Mixed-integer non-linear programming
MOP	Multi-objective programming
MP	Mathematical programming
MSFD	Multi-stage flash distillation
NLP	Non-linear programming
NZLD	Near-zero liquid discharge
PA	Pinch analysis
PI	Process integration
ORC	Organic Rankine cycle
PCM	Phase change material
SCBC	Supercritical CO ₂ Brayton cycle
TES	Thermal energy storage
WAHEN	Water Allocation and Heat Exchanger Network
WEIS	Water and Energy Integration Systems
WEN	Water-Energy Network
WHN	Water-Heat Nexus
WHR	Waste heat recovery

Parameters

h	Specific enthalpy (J/kg)
M	Mass flow rate (kg/s)
LHV	Fuel lower heating value (J/kg)
q	Transferred heat (W)

Subscripts

<i>additional</i>	Additional
<i>C.Air</i>	Combustion air stream
<i>cont.</i>	Contaminant
<i>Cooler</i>	Water system cooler
<i>CU</i>	Cold utility
<i>ExGas</i>	Exhaust gas stream
<i>Fuel</i>	Fuel stream
<i>Heater</i>	Water system heater
<i>HU</i>	Hot utility
<i>in</i>	Inlet
<i>initial</i>	Baseline scenario (with no measures implemented)
<i>LHV</i>	Lower heating value
<i>out</i>	Outlet
<i>recir.water</i>	Recirculated water stream
<i>useful</i>	Useful
<i>water</i>	Water stream
<i>WP</i>	Water-using process
<i>WWT</i>	Wastewater treatment unit

References

1. UNEP Water and Energy Efficiency: Information Brief 2014, 1–6. Available online: https://www.un.org/waterforlifedecade/pdf/01_2014_water_energy_efficiency.pdf (accessed on 1 June 2022).
2. Walsh, B.P.; Murray, S.N.; O’Sullivan, D.T.J. The water energy nexus, an ISO50001 water case study and the need for a water value system. *Water Resour. Ind.* **2015**, *10*, 15–28. [[CrossRef](#)]
3. Bauer, D. The Water-Energy Nexus: Challenges and Opportunities; US Department of Energy. 2014. Available online: <https://www.energy.gov/articles/water-energy-nexus-challenges-and-opportunities> (accessed on 1 June 2022).
4. Gabbar, H.A.; Abdelsalam, A.A. Energy—Water nexus: Integration, monitoring, KPIS tools and research vision. *Energies* **2020**, *13*, 6697. [[CrossRef](#)]
5. Sixt, G.N.; Strambo, C.; Zhang, J.; Chow, N.; Liu, J.; Han, G. Assessing the level of inter-sectoral policy integration for governance in the water-energy nexus: A comparative study of Los Angeles and Beijing. *Sustainability* **2020**, *12*, 7220. [[CrossRef](#)]
6. Ramos, H.M.; Morillo, J.G.; Rodríguez Diaz, J.A.; Carravetta, A.; McNabola, A. Sustainable water-energy nexus towards developing countries’ water sector efficiency. *Energies* **2021**, *14*, 3525. [[CrossRef](#)]
7. Saidur, R.; Hasanuzzaman, M.; Rahim, N.A. Energy Consumption, Energy Savings and Emission Analysis for Industrial Motors. In Proceedings of the 2010 International Conference on Industrial Engineering and Operations Management, Dhaka, Bangladesh, 9–10 January 2010.
8. Saidur, R. A review on electrical motors energy use and energy savings. *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* **2010**, *14*, 877–898. [[CrossRef](#)]
9. de Almeida, A.T.; Fonseca, P.; Bertoldi, P. Energy-efficient motor systems in the industrial and in the services sectors in the European Union: Characterisation, potentials, barriers and policies. *Energy* **2003**, *28*, 673–690. [[CrossRef](#)]
10. Vilanova, M.R.N.; Balestieri, J.A.P. Modeling of hydraulic and energy efficiency indicators for water supply systems. *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* **2015**, *48*, 540–557. [[CrossRef](#)]
11. Iten, M.; Oliveira, M.; Costa, D.; Michels, J. Water and energy efficiency improvement of steel wire manufacturing by circuit modelling and optimisation. *Energies* **2019**, *12*, 223. [[CrossRef](#)]
12. De Almeida, A.T.; Ferreira, F.J.T.E.; Both, D. Technical and economical considerations in the application of variable speed drives with electric motor systems. In Proceedings of the 2004 IEEE Industrial and Commercial Power Systems Technical, Clearwater Beach, FL, USA, 1–6 May 2004; pp. 136–144. [[CrossRef](#)]
13. Oliveira, M.C.; Iten, M.; Matos, H.A.; Michels, J. Water-energy nexus in typical industrial water circuits. *Water* **2019**, *11*, 699. [[CrossRef](#)]
14. Oliveira, M.C.; Iten, M. Modelling of industrial water circuits with a customised Modelica library. *Appl. Therm. Eng.* **2020**, *169*, 114840. [[CrossRef](#)]
15. Directive 2000/60/EC—WATER FRAMEWORK DIRECTIVE Directive 2000/60/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 October 2000 establishing a framework for Community action in the field of water policy. *Off. J. Eur. Parliam.* **2000**, *L327*, 1–82.
16. The European Parliament and The Council Directive 2012/27/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 October 2012 on Energy Efficiency, Amending Directives 2009/125/EC and 2010/30/EU and Repealing Directives 2004/8/EC and 2006/32/EC Text with EEA Relevance. Available online: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A32012L0027> (accessed on 8 June 2022).
17. European Commission The 2030 Climate & Energy Framework. Available online: <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/policies/climate-change/2030-climate-and-energy-framework/>. (accessed on 8 June 2022).
18. European Commission Energy and the Green Deal. Available online: https://ec.europa.eu/info/strategy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal/energy-and-green-deal_en (accessed on 8 June 2022).
19. Polley, G.T. Process Integration. Available online: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/topics/computer-science/process-integration> (accessed on 8 June 2022).
20. Relvas, S.; Fernandes, M.C.; Matos, H.A.; Nunes, C.P. *Integração de Processos—Uma Metodologia de Optimização Energética e Ambiental*; 2002; ISBN 972-95918-8-1. Available online: <https://bibliografia.bnportugal.gov.pt/bnp/bnp.exe/registo?1294541> (accessed on 10 June 2022).
21. Dunn, R.F.; Ristau, J.S. Using process integration technology to retrofit chemical plants for energy conservation and wastewater minimization. *Chem. Process Retrofit. Revamping Tech. Appl.* **2016**, 167–191. [[CrossRef](#)]
22. Castro Oliveira, M.; Iten, M.; Cruz, P.L.; Monteiro, H. Review on Energy Efficiency Progresses, Technologies and Strategies in the Ceramic Sector Focusing on Waste Heat Recovery. *Energies* **2020**, *13*, 6096. [[CrossRef](#)]
23. Oliveira, M.C.; Iten, M.; Matos, H.A. Assessment of energy efficiency improvement in ceramic industry through waste heat recovery modelling. *Comput. Aided Chem. Eng.* **2021**, *50*, 1653–1658. [[CrossRef](#)]
24. Castro Oliveira, M.; Iten, M. Modelling of A Solar Thermal Energy System For Energy Efficiency Improvement In A Ceramic Plant. *Renew. Energy Environ. Sustain.* **2021**, *6*, 31. [[CrossRef](#)]
25. Iten, M.; Fernandes, U.; Oliveira, M.C. Framework to assess eco-efficiency improvement: Case study of a meat production industry. *Energy Rep.* **2021**, *7*, 7134–7148. [[CrossRef](#)]
26. Oliveira, M.C.; Vieira, S.M.; Iten, M.; Matos, H.A. Optimisation of Water-Energy Networks in Process Industry: Implementation of Non-Linear and Multi-Objective Models. *Front. Chem. Eng.* **2022**, *3*, 750411. [[CrossRef](#)]
27. Fennema, O. Industrial sustainability: Lifting the siege on earth and our descendants. *Food Technol.* **2000**, *54*, 40–52+54.

28. Monteiro, H.; Cruz, P.L.; Oliveira, M.C.; Iten, M. Technical and economical assessment of waste heat recovery on a ceramic industry. In Proceedings of the Wastes: Solutions, Treatments and Opportunities III: Selected Papers from the 5th International Conference Wastes 2019, Lisbon, Portugal, 4–6 September 2020; pp. 524–530. [CrossRef]
29. Materi, S.; D'Angola, A.; Renna, P. A dynamic decision model for energy-efficient scheduling of manufacturing system with renewable energy supply. *J. Clean. Prod.* **2020**, *270*, 122028. [CrossRef]
30. Rajaeifar, M.A.; Sadeghzadeh Hemayati, S.; Tabatabaei, M.; Aghbashlo, M.; Mahmoudi, S.B. A review on beet sugar industry with a focus on implementation of waste-to-energy strategy for power supply. *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* **2019**, *103*, 423–442. [CrossRef]
31. Oliveira, H. Circular Economy: From Economic Concept to Legal Means for Sustainable Development. *E-Pública. Rev. Eletrónica. Direito Público.* **2020**, *7*, 73–93.
32. European Commission. *EU Strategy on Energy System Integration | Energy*; European Commission: Brussels, Belgium, 2020.
33. Theodore, L.; Dupont, R.R. Industrial Wastewater Treatment. Science Direct 2021. Available online: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/topics/earth-and-planetary-sciences/industrial-wastewater-treatment> (accessed on 10 June 2022).
34. Fallis, A. Waste Heat Recovery: Technology and Opportunities in U.S. Industry. *J. Chem. Inf. Model.* **2013**, *53*, 1689–1699.
35. Semmari, H.; Filali, A.; Aberkane, S.; Feidt, R.; Feidt, M. Flare gas waste heat recovery: Assessment of organic rankine cycle for electricity production and possible coupling with absorption chiller. *Energies* **2020**, *13*, 2265. [CrossRef]
36. Mezquita, A.; Boix, J.; Monfort, E.; Mallol, G. Energy saving in ceramic tile kilns: Cooling gas heat recovery. *Appl. Therm. Eng.* **2014**, *65*, 102–110. [CrossRef]
37. Klemes, J.J. Industrial water recycle/reuse. *Curr. Opin. Chem. Eng.* **2012**, *1*, 238–245. [CrossRef]
38. Salgot, M.; Folch, M. Wastewater treatment and water reuse. *Curr. Opin. Environ. Sci. Health* **2018**, *2*, 64–74. [CrossRef]
39. Ibrić, N.; Ahmetović, E.; Kravanja, Z. Mathematical programming synthesis of non-isothermal water networks by using a compact/reduced superstructure and an MINLP model. *Clean Technol. Environ. Policy* **2016**, *18*, 1779–1813. [CrossRef]
40. Dong, X.; Zhang, C.; Peng, X.; Chang, C.; Liao, Z.; Yang, Y.; Sun, J.; Wang, J.; Yang, Y. Simultaneous design of heat integrated water allocation networks considering all possible splitters and mixers. *Energy* **2022**, *238*, 121916. [CrossRef]
41. Gundersen, T. Heat Integration: Targets and Heat Exchanger Network Design. In *Handbook of Process Integration (PI), Minimisation of Energy and Water Use, Waste and Emissions*; Woodhead Publishing: John Solston, UK, 2013; pp. 129–167. [CrossRef]
42. Hong, X.; Liao, Z.; Jiang, B.; Wang, J.; Yang, Y. Targeting of heat integrated water allocation networks by one-step MILP formulation. *Appl. Energy* **2017**, *197*, 254–269. [CrossRef]
43. Hong, X.; Liao, Z.; Sun, J.; Jiang, B.; Wang, J.; Yang, Y. Energy and Water Management for Industrial Large-Scale Water Networks: A Systematic Simultaneous Optimization Approach. *ACS Sustain. Chem. Eng.* **2018**, *6*, 2269–2282. [CrossRef]
44. Hong, X.; Liao, Z.; Sun, J.; Jiang, B.; Wang, J.; Yang, Y. Heat Transfer Blocks Diagram: A Novel Tool for Targeting and Design of Heat Exchanger Networks Inside Heat Integrated Water Allocation Networks. *ACS Sustain. Chem. Eng.* **2018**, *6*, 2704–2715. [CrossRef]
45. Hou, Y.; Xie, W.; Duan, Z.; Wang, J. A conceptual methodology for simultaneous optimization of water and heat with non-isothermal mixing. *Front. Chem. Sci. Eng.* **2017**, *11*, 154–165. [CrossRef]
46. How, B.S.; Orosz, Á.; Teng, S.Y.; Lim, J.Y.; Friedler, F. Heat Integrated Water Regeneration Network Synthesis via Graph-Theoretic Sequential Method. *Chem. Eng. Trans.* **2021**, *88*, 49–54. [CrossRef]
47. Ibrić, N.; Ahmetović, E.; Kravanja, Z.; Grossmann, I.E. Simultaneous optimisation of large-scale problems of heat-integrated water networks. *Energy* **2021**, *235*, 121354. [CrossRef]
48. Kamat, S.; Bandyopadhyay, S. A hybrid approach for heat integration in water conservation networks through non-isothermal mixing. *Energy* **2021**, *233*, 121143. [CrossRef]
49. Kermani, M.; Kantor, I.D.; Maréchal, F. Synthesis of heat-integrated water allocation networks: A meta-analysis of solution strategies and network features. *Energies* **2018**, *11*, 1158. [CrossRef]
50. Ahmetović, E.; Ibrić, N.; Kravanja, Z.; Grossmann, I.E. Water and energy integration: A comprehensive literature review of non-isothermal water network synthesis. *Comput. Chem. Eng.* **2015**, *82*, 144–171. [CrossRef]
51. Kermani, M.; Kantor, I.D.; Maréchal, F. Optimal design of heat-integrated water allocation networks. *Energies* **2019**, *12*, 2174. [CrossRef]
52. Sahu, G.C.; Bandyopadhyay, S. Energy conservation in water allocation networks with negligible contaminant effects. *Chem. Eng. Sci.* **2010**, *65*, 4182–4193. [CrossRef]
53. Savulescu, L.E.; Alva-Argaez, A. Process Integration Concepts for Combined Energy and Water Integration. In *Handbook of Process Integration, Minimisation of Energy and Water Use, Waste and Emissions*; Woodhead Publishing: John Solston, UK, 2013; pp. 461–483. [CrossRef]
54. Souifi, M.; Souissi, A. Simultaneous water and energy saving in cooling water networks using pinch approach. *Mater. Today Proc.* **2019**, *13*, 1115–1124. [CrossRef]
55. Yan, F.; Wu, H.; Li, W.; Zhang, J. Simultaneous optimization of heat-integrated water networks by a nonlinear program. *Chem. Eng. Sci.* **2016**, *140*, 76–89. [CrossRef]
56. Zhao, H.P.; Yang, Y.; Liu, Z.Y. Design of heat integrated water networks with multiple contaminants. *J. Clean. Prod.* **2019**, *211*, 530–536. [CrossRef]

57. Zhelev, T.K.; Zheleva, S.R. Combined pinch analysis for more efficient energy and water resources management in beverage industry. *Waste Manag. Environ.* **2002**, *56*, 623–632.
58. Zheng, X.S.; Feng, X.; Cao, D.L. Design water allocation network with minimum freshwater and energy consumption. *Comput. Aided Chem. Eng.* **2003**, *15*, 388–393. [[CrossRef](#)]
59. Ahmetović, E.; Kravanja, Z. Simultaneous synthesis of process water and heat exchanger networks. *Energy* **2013**, *57*, 236–250. [[CrossRef](#)]
60. Alnouri, S.Y.; Linke, P.; El-Halwagi, M. Water integration in industrial zones: A spatial representation with direct recycle applications. *Clean Technol. Environ. Policy* **2014**, *16*, 1637–1659. [[CrossRef](#)]
61. Boix, M.; Pibouleau, L.; Montastruc, L.; Azzaro-Pantel, C.; Domenech, S. Minimizing water and energy consumptions in water and heat exchange networks. *Appl. Therm. Eng.* **2012**, *36*, 442–455. [[CrossRef](#)]
62. Caballero, J.A.; Pavão, L.V.; Costa, C.B.B.; Ravagnani, M.A.S.S. A Novel Sequential Approach for the Design of Heat Exchanger Networks. *Front. Chem. Eng.* **2021**, *3*, 733186. [[CrossRef](#)]
63. Chijin, Z.; Congjing, R.; Zuwei, L.; Jingyuan, S.; Jingdai, W.; Yongrong, Y. Recent Progresses on Optimal Design of Heat Integrated Water Allocation Network. *China Pet. Process. Petrochemical. Technol.* **2021**, *23*, 69–75.
64. Chin, H.H.; Foo, D.C.Y.; Lam, H.L. Simultaneous water and energy integration with isothermal and non-isothermal mixing—A P-graph approach. *Resour. Conserv. Recycl.* **2019**, *149*, 687–713. [[CrossRef](#)]
65. Dong, H.G.; Lin, C.Y.; Chang, C.T. Simultaneous optimization approach for integrated water-allocation and heat-exchange networks. *Chem. Eng. Sci.* **2008**, *63*, 3664–3678. [[CrossRef](#)]
66. Ribera-Pi, J.; Badia-Fabregat, M.; Arias, D.; Gómez, V.; Taberna, E.; Sanz, J.; Martínez-Lladó, X.; Jubany, I. Coagulation-flocculation and moving bed biofilm reactor as pre-treatment for water recycling in the petrochemical industry. *Sci. Total Environ.* **2020**, *715*, 136800. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
67. Skouteris, G.; Ouki, S.; Foo, D.; Saroj, D.; Altini, M.; Melidis, P.; Cowley, B.; Ells, G.; Palmer, S.; O'Dell, S. Water footprint and water pinch analysis techniques for sustainable water management in the brick-manufacturing industry. *J. Clean. Prod.* **2018**, *172*, 786–794. [[CrossRef](#)]
68. Gherghel, A.; Teodosiu, C.; De Gisi, S. A review on wastewater sludge valorisation and its challenges in the context of circular economy. *J. Clean. Prod.* **2019**, *228*, 244–263. [[CrossRef](#)]
69. Fernandes, M.; Nunes, C.; Gomes, P. *Medidas Transversais de Eficiência Energética Para a Indústria*; Direção-Geral de Energia e Geologia: Lisbon, Portugal, 2016; ISBN 978-972-8268-41-1.
70. Miró, L.; Gasia, J.; Cabeza, L.F. Thermal energy storage (TES) for industrial waste heat (IWH) recovery: A review. *Appl. Energy* **2016**, *179*, 284–301. [[CrossRef](#)]
71. Rahimi, B.; Chua, H.T. *Low Grade Heat Driven Multi-Effect Distillation and Desalination*; Elsevier: Amsterdam, The Netherlands, 2017; ISBN 9780128052709.
72. Widmann, D.; Mader, H.; Friedrich, H.; Heywang, W.; Müller, R. Process Integration. Available online: <https://www.ceas.manchester.ac.uk/research/themes/process-integration/> (accessed on 10 June 2022).
73. Singhvi, A.; Shenoy, U. V Pinch Analysis. Available online: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/topics/engineering/pinch-analysis> (accessed on 10 June 2022).
74. Klemeš, J.J.; Varbanov, P.S.; Walmsley, T.G.; Jia, X. New directions in the implementation of Pinch Methodology (PM). *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* **2018**, *98*, 439–468. [[CrossRef](#)]
75. Castier, M. Pinch analysis revisited: New rules for utility targeting. *Appl. Therm. Eng.* **2007**, *27*, 1653–1656. [[CrossRef](#)]
76. Friedler, F. Process integration, modelling and optimisation for energy saving and pollution reduction. *Appl. Therm. Eng.* **2010**, *30*, 2270–2280. [[CrossRef](#)]
77. Klemeš, J.; Perry, S.J.; Bulatov, I. Towards sustainable energy systems-role and achievements of heat integration. *Chem. Eng.* **2007**. Available online: <https://www.irbnet.de/daten/iconda/CIB7696.pdf> (accessed on 10 June 2022).
78. Gadalla, M.A. A novel graphical technique for Pinch Analysis applications: Energy Targets and grassroots design. *Energy Convers. Manag.* **2015**, *96*, 499–510. [[CrossRef](#)]
79. Heat Integration. Available online: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/topics/engineering/heat-integration> (accessed on 10 June 2022).
80. Foo, D. Water Pinch Analysis. Available online: <https://www.cii-twi.in/water-pinch.html> (accessed on 10 June 2022).
81. Manan, Z.A.; Tan, Y.L.; Foo, D.C.Y. Targeting the minimum water flow rate using water cascade analysis technique. *AIChE J.* **2004**, *50*, 3169–3183. [[CrossRef](#)]
82. Yoro, K.O.; Sekoai, P.T.; Isafiade, A.J.; Daramola, M.O. A review on heat and mass integration techniques for energy and material minimization during CO₂ capture. *Int. J. Energy Environ. Eng.* **2019**, *10*, 367–387. [[CrossRef](#)]
83. Klemeš, J.J.; Kravanja, Z. Forty years of Heat Integration: Pinch Analysis (PA) and Mathematical Programming (MP). *Curr. Opin. Chem. Eng.* **2013**, *2*, 461–474. [[CrossRef](#)]
84. Klemeš, J.J.; Varbanov, P.S. From HEN to Total Site, to Energy Supply Chains. *Chalmers.Se* 2012. Available online: <http://www.chalmers.se/en/areas-of-advance/energy/Documents/Process%20Integration%20Conference%202013/Presentations/Jiri%20Klimes.pdf> (accessed on 10 June 2022).
85. Jain, S.; Bandyopadhyay, S. Multi-objective optimisation for segregated targeting problems using Pinch Analysis. *J. Clean. Prod.* **2019**, *221*, 339–352. [[CrossRef](#)]

86. Thibault, F.; Zoughaib, A.; Pelloux-Prayer, S. A MILP algorithm for utilities pre-design based on the Pinch Analysis and an exergy criterion. *Comput. Chem. Eng.* **2015**, *75*, 65–73. [[CrossRef](#)]
87. Zhou, C.; Zhuang, Y.; Zhang, L.; Liu, L.; Du, J.; Shen, S. A novel pinch-based method for process integration and optimization of Kalina cycle. *Energy Convers. Manag.* **2020**, *209*, 112630. [[CrossRef](#)]
88. Angsutorn, N.; Siemanond, K.; Chuvaree, R. Heat exchanger network synthesis using MINLP Stage-wise model with pinch analysis and relaxation. *Comput. Aided Chem. Eng.* **2014**, *33*, 139–144. [[CrossRef](#)]
89. Yoon, S.G.; Lee, J.; Park, S. Heat integration analysis for an industrial ethylbenzene plant using pinch analysis. *Appl. Therm. Eng.* **2007**, *27*, 886–893. [[CrossRef](#)]
90. Geldermann, J.; Treitz, M.; Rentz, O. Integrated technique assessment based on the pinch analysis approach for the design of production networks. *Eur. J. Oper. Res.* **2006**, *171*, 1020–1032. [[CrossRef](#)]
91. Elias, A.M.; de Campos Giordano, R.; Secchi, A.R.; Furlan, F.F. Integrating pinch analysis and process simulation within equation-oriented simulators. *Comput. Chem. Eng.* **2019**, *130*, 106555. [[CrossRef](#)]
92. Bonhivers, J.C.; Moussavi, A.; Alva-Argaez, A.; Stuart, P.R. Linking pinch analysis and bridge analysis to save energy by heat-exchanger network retrofit. *Appl. Therm. Eng.* **2016**, *106*, 443–472. [[CrossRef](#)]
93. Valiani, S.; Tahouni, N.; Panjeshahi, M.H. Optimization of pre-combustion capture for thermal power plants using Pinch Analysis. *Energy* **2017**, *119*, 950–960. [[CrossRef](#)]
94. Han, T.; Wang, C.; Zhu, C.; Che, D. Optimization of waste heat recovery power generation system for cement plant by combining pinch and exergy analysis methods. *Appl. Therm. Eng.* **2018**, *140*, 334–340. [[CrossRef](#)]
95. Roychaudhuri, P.S.; Kazantzi, V.; Foo, D.C.Y.; Tan, R.R.; Bandyopadhyay, S. Selection of energy conservation projects through Financial Pinch Analysis. *Energy* **2017**, *138*, 602–615. [[CrossRef](#)]
96. Manizadeh, A.; Entezari, A.; Ahmadi, R. The energy and economic target optimization of a naphtha production unit by implementing energy pinch technology. *Case Stud. Therm. Eng.* **2018**, *12*, 396–404. [[CrossRef](#)]
97. Olsen, D.; Abdelouadoud, Y.; Liem, P.; Wellig, B. The Role of Pinch Analysis for Industrial ORC Integration. *Energy Procedia* **2017**, *129*, 74–81. [[CrossRef](#)]
98. Abdelouadoud, Y.; Lucas, E.; Krummenacher, P.; Olsen, D.; Wellig, B. Batch process heat storage integration: A simple and effective graphical approach. *Energy* **2019**, *185*, 804–818. [[CrossRef](#)]
99. Zhelev, T.K.; Semkov, K.A. Cleaner flue gas and energy recovery through pinch analysis. *J. Clean. Prod.* **2004**, *12*, 165–170. [[CrossRef](#)]
100. Araújo, V.E.; Bernardo, F.P.; Reis, C.M.; Martins, F.G. Cluster Analysis of Process Operational Data to Identify Representative Scenarios for Pinch Analysis and Energy Optimisation Studies. *Comput. Aided Chem. Eng.* **2017**, *40*, 2539–2544. [[CrossRef](#)]
101. Hamsani, M.N.; Walmsley, T.G.; Liew, P.Y.; Wan Alwi, S.R. Combined Pinch and exergy numerical analysis for low temperature heat exchanger network. *Energy* **2018**, *153*, 100–112. [[CrossRef](#)]
102. Feng, X.; Zhu, X.X. Combining pinch and exergy analysis for process modifications. *Appl. Therm. Eng.* **1997**, *17*, 249–261. [[CrossRef](#)]
103. Salama, A.I.A. Determination of the optimal heat energy targets in heat pinch analysis using a geometry-based approach. *Comput. Chem. Eng.* **2006**, *30*, 758–764. [[CrossRef](#)]
104. Ghannadzadeh, A.; Sadeqzadeh, M. Exergy aided pinch analysis to enhance energy integration towards environmental sustainability in a chlorine-caustic soda production process. *Appl. Therm. Eng.* **2017**, *125*, 1518–1529. [[CrossRef](#)]
105. Pereira, P.M.; Fernandes, M.C.; Matos, H.A. F12EPI—A freeware tool for performing Heat Integration based on Pinch Analysis. *Comput. Aided Chem. Eng.* **2016**, *38*, 1815–1820. [[CrossRef](#)]
106. Khezri, S.M.; Lotfi, F.; Tabibian, S.; Erfani, Z. Application of water pinch technology for water and wastewater minimization in aluminum anodizing industries. *Int. J. Environ. Sci. Technol.* **2010**, *7*, 281–290. [[CrossRef](#)]
107. Liu, Z.Y.; Yang, Y.Z.; Zhang, Y. Determining the pinch point and calculating the freshwater target for water-using systems with single contaminant. *Chem. Eng. Res. Des.* **2007**, *85*, 1485–1490. [[CrossRef](#)]
108. Jia, X.; Zhang, L.; Li, Z.; Tan, R.R.; Dou, J.; Foo, D.C.Y.; Wang, F. Pinch analysis for targeting desalinated water price subsidy. *J. Clean. Prod.* **2019**, *227*, 950–959. [[CrossRef](#)]
109. Tan, Y.L.; Manan, Z.A.; Foo, D.C.Y. Retrofit of water network with regeneration using water pinch analysis. *Process Saf. Environ. Prot.* **2007**, *85*, 305–317. [[CrossRef](#)]
110. Sorin, M.; Bédard, S. The Global Pinch Point in water reuse networks. *Process Saf. Environ. Prot.* **1999**, *77*, 305–308. [[CrossRef](#)]
111. Bavar, M.; Sarrafzadeh, M.H.; Asgharnejad, H.; Norouzi-Firouz, H. Water management methods in food industry: Corn refinery as a case study. *J. Food Eng.* **2018**, *238*, 78–84. [[CrossRef](#)]
112. Wan Alwi, S.R.; Manan, Z.A. Water Pinch Analysis for Water Management and Minimisation: An Introduction. In *Handbook of Process Integration, Minimisation of Energy and Water Use, Waste and Emissions*; Woodhead Publishing: John Solston, UK, 2013; pp. 353–382. [[CrossRef](#)]
113. Mohammadnejad, S.; Bidhendi, G.R.N.; Mehrdadi, N. Water pinch analysis in oil refinery using regeneration reuse and recycling consideration. *Desalination* **2011**, *265*, 255–265. [[CrossRef](#)]
114. Zoller, F. Integration of energy networks and the water cycle with surface water energy as connecting element. In *Proceedings of the 12th IEA Heat Pump Conference 2017, Rotterdam, The Netherlands, 15–18 May 2017*.

115. Tan, R.R.; Foo, D.C.Y. Pinch Analysis for Sustainable Energy Planning Using Diverse Quality Measures. In *Handbook of Process Integration, Minimisation of Energy and Water Use, Waste and Emissions*; Woodhead Publishing: John Solston, UK, 2013; pp. 505–523. [CrossRef]
116. Lim, X.Y.; Foo, D.C.Y.; Tan, R.R. Pinch analysis for the planning of power generation sector in the United Arab Emirates: A climate-energy-water nexus study. *J. Clean. Prod.* **2018**, *180*, 11–19. [CrossRef]
117. Silori, G.K.; Khanam, S. Simultaneous water and energy integration techniques: A review. *Technology* **2017**, *15*, 30.
118. Jouhara, H.; Khordehgah, N.; Almahmoud, S.; Delpech, B.; Chauhan, A.; Tassou, S.A. Waste heat recovery technologies and applications. *Therm. Sci. Eng. Prog.* **2018**, *6*, 268–289. [CrossRef]
119. Brückner, S.; Liu, S.; Miró, L.; Radspieler, M.; Cabeza, L.F.; Lävemann, E. Industrial waste heat recovery technologies: An economic analysis of heat transformation technologies. *Appl. Energy* **2015**, *151*, 157–167. [CrossRef]
120. Sarbu, I.; Sebarchievici, C. A comprehensive review of thermal energy storage. *Sustain.* **2018**, *10*, 191. [CrossRef]
121. Royo, P.; Acevedo, L.; Arnal, Á.J.; Diaz-Ramírez, M.; García-Armingol, T.; Ferreira, V.J.; Ferreira, G.; López-Sabirón, A.M. Decision support system of innovative high-temperature latent heat storage for waste heat recovery in the energy-intensive industry. *Energies* **2021**, *14*, 365. [CrossRef]
122. Wallin, J.; Madani, H.; Claesson, J. Run-around coil ventilation heat recovery system: A comparative study between different system configurations. *Appl. Energy* **2012**, *90*, 258–265. [CrossRef]
123. Varghese, B.; Das, D.; Devassy, D.; Harikrishnan, K.; Sharath, S.G. Design and Cost Optimization of Plate Heat Exchanger. *Res. Inven. Int. J. Eng. Sci. Issn* **2014**, *4*, 43–48.
124. Cipollone, R.; Bianchi, G.; Di Battista, D.; Fatigati, F. Experimental and numerical analyses on a plate heat exchanger with phase change for waste heat recovery at off-design conditions. *J. Phys. Conf. Ser.* **2015**, *655*, 012038. [CrossRef]
125. Faghri, A. Heat Pipes: Review, Opportunities and Challenges. *Front. Heat Pipes* **2014**, *5*, 1. [CrossRef]
126. Delpech, B.; Milani, M.; Montorsi, L.; Boscardin, D.; Chauhan, A.; Almahmoud, S.; Axcell, B.; Jouhara, H. Energy efficiency enhancement and waste heat recovery in industrial processes by means of the heat pipe technology: Case of the ceramic industry. *Energy* **2018**, *158*, 656–665. [CrossRef]
127. Jouhara, H.; Chauhan, A.; Nannou, T.; Almahmoud, S.; Delpech, B.; Wrobel, L.C. Heat pipe based systems—Advances and applications. *Energy* **2017**, *128*, 729–754. [CrossRef]
128. Nimbalkar, S. Waste Heat Recovery from Industrial Process Heating Equipment. *Oak Ridge Natl. Lab.* **2015**. Available online: <https://www.scribd.com/document/367470421/IAC-Student-Webinar-May-Sachin> (accessed on 10 June 2022).
129. Shah, R.K.; Sekuli, D.P. Fundamentals of Heat Exchanger Design. In *Fundamentals of Heat Exchanger Design*; John Wiley & Sons: Hoboken, NJ, USA, 2003. [CrossRef]
130. The National Productivity Council, I. *Waste Heat Recovery*; United Nations Environment Programme: Nairobi, Kenya, 2006.
131. Canada. Agriculture Canada. Food Production and Inspection Branch. In *Marketing and Economics Branch. Heat Recovery for Canadian Food and Beverage Industries*; Agriculture Canada; 1984; p. 28. Available online: https://publications.gc.ca/collections/collection_2012/agr/A15-5181-1984-eng.pdf (accessed on 10 June 2022).
132. *Guwahati Waste Heat Recovery Through Heat Exchangers*; Indian Institute of Technology Guwahati: Assam, India, 2017.
133. *Carbon Trust Heat Recovery*; Carbon Trust Ltd.: London, UK, 2011.
134. Aghayari, R.; Maddah, H.; Ashori, F.; Hakiminejad, A.; Aghili, M. Effect of nanoparticles on heat transfer in mini double-pipe heat exchangers in turbulent flow. *Heat Mass Transf. Und Stoffuebertragung* **2015**, *51*, 301–306. [CrossRef]
135. Spirax Sarco Miscellaneous Boiler Types Economisers and Superheaters. Available online: <https://www.spiraxsarco.com/learn-about-steam/the-boiler-house/miscellaneous-boiler-types-economisers-and-superheaters> (accessed on 10 June 2022).
136. U.S. Department of Energy. *Use Feedwater Economizers for Waste Heat Recovery*; Office of Energy Efficiency and Renewable Energy: Washington, DC, USA, 2012. Available online: https://www.energy.gov/sites/prod/files/2014/05/f16/steam3_recovery.pdf (accessed on 10 June 2022).
137. Thermtech. Reducing Energy Costs with Economisers. Available online: <http://thermtech.co.uk/reducing-energy-costs-with-economisers/> (accessed on 10 June 2022).
138. *Mohan Sen Basic Mechanical Engineering*; Laxmi Publications: Delhi, India, 2016.
139. Steam Generation Economiser Units. Available online: <http://steamgeneration.co.za/cochran-economiser-units/> (accessed on 10 June 2022).
140. PEI—Power Engineering International Heat Recovery Steam Generators Design Options and Benefits. Available online: <https://www.powerengineeringint.com/coal-fired/equipment-coal-fired/heat-recovery-steam-generators-design-options-and-benefits/> (accessed on 10 June 2022).
141. ScienceDirect Heat Recovery Steam Generator. Available online: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/topics/engineering/heat-recovery-steam-generator> (accessed on 10 June 2022).
142. Quoilin, S.; Van Den Broek, M.; Declaye, S.; Dewallef, P.; Lemort, V. Techno-economic survey of organic rankine cycle (ORC) systems. *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* **2013**, *22*, 168–186. [CrossRef]
143. Wang, D.; Ling, X.; Peng, H. Performance analysis of double organic Rankine cycle for discontinuous low temperature waste heat recovery. *Appl. Therm. Eng.* **2012**, *48*, 63–71. [CrossRef]
144. Turboden ORC System. Available online: <https://www.turboden.com/products/2463/orc-system> (accessed on 10 June 2022).

145. Saleh, B.; Koglbauer, G.; Wendland, M.; Fischer, J. Working fluids for low-temperature organic Rankine cycles. *Energy* **2007**, *32*, 1210–1221. [[CrossRef](#)]
146. Douvartzides, S.; Karmalis, I. Working fluid selection for the Organic Rankine Cycle (ORC) exhaust heat recovery of an internal combustion engine power plant. In *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*; IOP Publishing Ltd.: Bristol, UK, 2016; p. 161. [[CrossRef](#)]
147. Roy, J.P.; Mishra, M.K.; Misra, A. Parametric optimization and performance analysis of a waste heat recovery system using Organic Rankine Cycle. *Energy* **2010**, *35*, 5049–5062. [[CrossRef](#)]
148. Roy, J.P.; Mishra, M.K.; Misra, A. Parametric optimization and performance analysis of a regenerative Organic Rankine Cycle using low-grade waste heat for power generation. *Int. J. Green Energy* **2011**, *8*, 173–196. [[CrossRef](#)]
149. Delpech, B.; Axcell, B.; Jouhara, H. A review on waste heat recovery from exhaust in the ceramics industry. *E3S Web Conf.* **2017**, *22*, 8. [[CrossRef](#)]
150. Mlcak, H.A. An Introduction to the Kalina Cycle. *Proc. Int. Jt. Power Gener. Conf.* **1996**, *30*, 1–11.
151. Mirolli, M.D. Kalina Cycle Power Systems in Waste Heat Recovery Applications. Available online: <http://www.globalcement.com/magazine/articles/721-kalina-cycle-power-systems-in-waste-heat-recovery-applications> (accessed on 10 June 2022).
152. Rogdakis, E.; Lolos, P. Kalina Cycles for Power Generation. In *Handbook of Clean Energy Systems*; John Wiley & Sons, Ltd.: Hoboken, NJ, USA, 2015; pp. 1–25. [[CrossRef](#)]
153. Wang, J.; Wang, J.; Zhao, P.; Dai, Y.; Peng, Y. Thermodynamic analysis and comparison study of an Organic Rankine Cycle (ORC) and a Kalina cycle for waste heat recovery of compressor intercooling. *Proc. ASME Turbo Expo* **2014**, *3B*, 1–10. [[CrossRef](#)]
154. Milewski, J.; Krasucki, J. Comparison of ORC and Kalina cycles for waste heat recovery in the steel industry. *J. Power Technol.* **2017**, *97*, 302–307.
155. Júnior, E.P.B.; Arrieta, M.D.P.; Arrieta, F.R.P.; Silva, C.H.F. Assessment of a Kalina cycle for waste heat recovery in the cement industry. *Appl. Therm. Eng.* **2019**, *147*, 421–437. [[CrossRef](#)]
156. Manente, G.; Costa, M. On the conceptual design of novel supercritical CO₂ power cycles for waste heat recovery. In Proceedings of the ECOS 2019—32nd International Conference on Efficiency, Cost, Optimization, Simulation and Environmental Impact of Energy Systems, Wroclaw, Poland, 23–28 June 2019; pp. 2219–2231.
157. Patel, S. What Are Supercritical CO₂ Power Cycles? Available online: <https://www.powermag.com/what-are-supercritical-co2-power-cycles/> (accessed on 11 May 2022).
158. Liu, Y.; Wang, Y.; Huang, D. Supercritical CO₂ Brayton cycle: A state-of-the-art review. *Energy* **2019**, *189*, 115900. [[CrossRef](#)]
159. Maestre-Cambronel, D.; Guzmán Barros, J.; Gonzalez-Quiroga, A.; Bula, A.; Duarte-Forero, J. Thermoeconomic analysis of improved exhaust waste heat recovery system for natural gas engine based on Vortex Tube heat booster and supercritical CO₂ Brayton cycle. *Sustain. Energy Technol. Assessments* **2021**, *47*, 101355. [[CrossRef](#)]
160. Kumar, K.; Singh, S. Investigating thermal stratification in a vertical hot water storage tank under multiple transient operations. *Energy Rep.* **2021**, *7*, 7186–7199. [[CrossRef](#)]
161. Li, Q.; Huang, X.; Tai, Y.; Gao, W.; Wenxian, L.; Liu, W. Thermal stratification in a solar hot water storage tank with mantle heat exchanger. *Renew. Energy* **2021**, *173*, 1–11. [[CrossRef](#)]
162. Puschnigg, S.; Lindorfer, J.; Moser, S.; Kienberger, T. Techno-economic aspects of increasing primary energy efficiency in industrial branches using thermal energy storage. *J. Energy Storage* **2021**, *36*, 102344. [[CrossRef](#)]
163. Rosen, M.A. Thermal Storage. Available online: <https://www.greenspec.co.uk/building-design/thermal-storage/> (accessed on 10 June 2022).
164. *International Renewable Energy Agency Innovation Outlook: Thermal Energy Storage*; International Renewable Energy Agency: Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates, 2020; p. 144.
165. Canbazoglu, S.; Şahinaslan, A.; Ekmekyapar, A.; Aksoy, Y.G.; Akarsu, F. Enhancement of solar thermal energy storage performance using sodium thiosulfate pentahydrate of a conventional solar water-heating system. *Energy Build.* **2005**, *37*, 235–242. [[CrossRef](#)]
166. Koca, A.; Oztop, H.F.; Koyun, T.; Varol, Y. Energy and exergy analysis of a latent heat storage system with phase change material for a solar collector. *Renew. Energy* **2008**, *33*, 567–574. [[CrossRef](#)]
167. Chaabane, M.; Mhiri, H.; Bournot, P. Thermal performance of an integrated collector storage solar water heater (ICSSWH) with phase change materials (PCM). *Energy Convers. Manag.* **2014**, *78*, 897–903. [[CrossRef](#)]
168. Douvi, E.; Pagkalos, C.; Dogkas, G.; Koukou, M.K.; Stathopoulos, V.N.; Caouris, Y.; Vrachopoulos, M.G. Phase change materials in solar domestic hot water systems: A review. *Int. J. Thermofluids* **2021**, *10*, 100075. [[CrossRef](#)]
169. Lee, W.S.; Chen, B.R.; Chen, S.L. Latent heat storage in a two-phase thermosiphon solar water heater. *J. Sol. Energy Eng. Trans. ASME* **2006**, *128*, 69–76. [[CrossRef](#)]
170. Chopra, K.; Tyagi, V.V.; Pandey, A.K.; Sharma, R.K.; Sari, A. PCM integrated glass in glass tube solar collector for low and medium temperature applications: Thermodynamic & techno-economic approach. *Energy* **2020**, *198*, 117238. [[CrossRef](#)]
171. Wu, W.; Dai, S.; Liu, Z.; Dou, Y.; Hua, J.; Li, M.; Wang, X.; Wang, X. Experimental study on the performance of a novel solar water heating system with and without PCM. *Sol. Energy* **2018**, *171*, 604–612. [[CrossRef](#)]
172. Naghavi, M.S.; Ang, B.C.; Rahmanian, B.; Naghavi, S.; Bazri, S.; Mahmoodian, R.; Metselaar, H.S.C. On-demand dynamic performance of a thermal battery in tankless domestic solar water heating in the tropical region. *Appl. Therm. Eng.* **2020**, *167*, 114790. [[CrossRef](#)]

173. Ben Zohra, M.; Riad, A.; Alhamany, A. Development of thermal energy storage system based on phase change materials. In Proceedings of the 2019 International Conference of Computer Science and Renewable Energies (ICCSRE), Agadir, Morocco, 22–24 July 2019. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
174. Royo, P.; Ferreira, V.J.; Ure, Z.; Gledhill, S.; López-Sabirón, A.M.; Ferreira, G. Multiple-Criteria Decision Analysis and characterisation of phase change materials for waste heat recovery at high temperature for sustainable energy-intensive industry. *Mater. Des.* **2020**, *186*, 108215. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
175. Sharif, M.K.A.; Al-Abidi, A.A.; Mat, S.; Sopian, K.; Ruslan, M.H.; Sulaiman, M.Y.; Rosli, M.A.M. Review of the application of phase change material for heating and domestic hot water systems. *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* **2015**, *42*, 557–568. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
176. Abokersh, M.H.; Osman, M.; El-Baz, O.; El-Morsi, M.; Sharaf, O. Review of the phase change material (PCM) usage for solar domestic water heating systems (SDWHS). *Int. J. Energy Res.* **2018**, *42*, 329–357. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
177. Faraj, K.; Khaled, M.; Faraj, J.; Hachem, F.; Castelain, C. A review on phase change materials for thermal energy storage in buildings: Heating and hybrid applications. *J. Energy Storage* **2021**, *33*, 101913. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
178. Yang, L.; Xu, H.; Cola, F.; Akhmetov, B.; Gil, A.; Cabeza, L.F.; Romagnoli, A. Shell-and-tube latent heat thermal energy storage design methodology with material selection, storage performance evaluation, and cost minimization. *Appl. Sci.* **2021**, *11*, 4180. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
179. Kumar, B. *Design, Development and Performance Evaluation of a Latent Heat Storage Unit for Evening and Morning Hot Water Using a Box Type Solar Collector*; Project Report, M. Tech. (Energy Management); School of Energy and Environmental Studies, Devi Ahilya University: Indore, India, 2001.
180. Hamed, M.; Fallah, A.; Brahim, A. Ben Numerical analysis of an integrated storage solar heater. *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy* **2017**, *42*, 8721–8732. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
181. Palacio, M.; Carmona, M. Experimental Evaluation of a Latent Heat Thermal Storage Unit Integrated into a Flat Plate Solar Collector as Temperature Stabilizer. In Proceedings of the 2018 2nd International Conference on Green Energy and Applications (ICGEA), Singapore, 24–26 March 2018; pp. 83–87. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
182. Allouhi, A.; Ait Msaad, A.; Benzakour Amine, M.; Saidur, R.; Mahdaoui, M.; Kousksou, T.; Pandey, A.K.; Jamil, A.; Moujibi, N.; Benbassou, A. Optimization of melting and solidification processes of PCM: Application to integrated collector storage solar water heaters (ICSSWH). *Sol. Energy* **2018**, *171*, 562–570. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
183. Koyuncu, T.; Lüle, F. Thermal Performance of a Domestic Chromium Solar Water Collector with Phase Change Material. *Procedia Soc. Behav. Sci.* **2015**, *195*, 2430–2442. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
184. El Qarnia, H. Numerical analysis of a coupled solar collector latent heat storage unit using various phase change materials for heating the water. *Energy Convers. Manag.* **2009**, *50*, 247–254. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
185. Varol, Y.; Koca, A.; Oztop, H.F.; Avci, E. Forecasting of thermal energy storage performance of Phase Change Material in a solar collector using soft computing techniques. *Expert Syst. Appl.* **2010**, *37*, 2724–2732. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
186. Tarhan, S.; Sari, A.; Yardim, M.H. Temperature distributions in trapezoidal built in storage solar water heaters with/without phase change materials. *Energy Convers. Manag.* **2006**, *47*, 2143–2154. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
187. Motte, F.; Notton, G.; Lamnatou, C.; Cristofari, C.; Chemisana, D. Numerical study of PCM integration impact on overall performances of a highly building-integrated solar collector. *Renew. Energy* **2019**, *137*, 10–19. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
188. Palacio, M.; Rincón, A.; Carmona, M. Experimental comparative analysis of a flat plate solar collector with and without PCM. *Sol. Energy* **2020**, *206*, 708–721. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
189. Feliński, P.; Sekret, R. Effect of PCM application inside an evacuated tube collector on the thermal performance of a domestic hot water system. *Energy Build.* **2017**, *152*, 558–567. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
190. Prakash, J.; Roan, D.; Tauqir, W.; Nazir, H.; Ali, M.; Kannan, A. Off-grid solar thermal water heating system using phase-change materials: Design, integration and real environment investigation. *Appl. Energy* **2019**, *240*, 73–83. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
191. Naghavi, M.S.; Ong, K.S.; Badruddin, I.A.; Mehrali, M.; Metselaar, H.S.C. Thermal performance of a compact design heat pipe solar collector with latent heat storage in charging/discharging modes. *Energy* **2017**, *127*, 101–115. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
192. Bilardo, M.; Fraise, G.; Pailha, M.; Fabrizio, E. Modelling and performance analysis of a new concept of integral collector storage (ICS) with phase change material. *Sol. Energy* **2019**, *183*, 425–440. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
193. Bilardo, M.; Fraise, G.; Pailha, M.; Fabrizio, E. Design and experimental analysis of an Integral Collector Storage (ICS) prototype for DHW production. *Appl. Energy* **2020**, *259*, 114104. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
194. Shabgard, H.; Song, L.; Zhu, W. Heat transfer and exergy analysis of a novel solar-powered integrated heating, cooling, and hot water system with latent heat thermal energy storage. *Energy Convers. Manag.* **2018**, *175*, 121–131. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
195. Reddy, K.S. Thermal modeling of PCM-based solar integrated collector storage water heating system. *J. Sol. Energy Eng. Trans. ASME* **2007**, *129*, 458–464. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
196. Bouadila, S.; Fteiti, M.; Oueslati, M.M.; Guizani, A.; Farhat, A. Enhancement of latent heat storage in a rectangular cavity: Solar water heater case study. *Energy Convers. Manag.* **2014**, *78*, 904–912. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
197. Khalifa, A.J.N.; Suffer, K.H.; Mahmoud, M.S. A storage domestic solar hot water system with a back layer of phase change material. *Exp. Therm. Fluid Sci.* **2013**, *44*, 174–181. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
198. Mettawee, E.B.S.; Assassa, G.M.R. Experimental study of a compact PCM solar collector. *Energy* **2006**, *31*, 2958–2968. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
199. Panayiotou, G.P.; Kalogirou, S.A.; Tassou, S.A. Evaluation of the application of Phase Change Materials (PCM) on the envelope of a typical dwelling in the Mediterranean region. *Renew. Energy* **2016**, *97*, 24–32. [\[CrossRef\]](#)

200. Mahfuz, M.H.; Anisur, M.R.; Kibria, M.A.; Saidur, R.; Metselaar, I.H.S.C. Performance investigation of thermal energy storage system with Phase Change Material (PCM) for solar water heating application. *Int. Commun. Heat Mass Transf.* **2014**, *57*, 132–139. [[CrossRef](#)]
201. Cuviella-Suárez, C.; Colmenar-Santos, A.; Borge-Diez, D.; López-Rey, Á. Heat recovery in sanitary-ware industry applied to water and energy saving by multi-effect distillation. *J. Clean. Prod.* **2019**, *213*, 1322–1336. [[CrossRef](#)]
202. Rahimi, B.; Chua, H.T. Low Grade Sensible Heat-Driven Distillation. In *Low Grade Heat Driven Multi-Effect Distillation and Desalination*; Elsevier: Amsterdam, The Netherlands, 2017; pp. 19–26. [[CrossRef](#)]
203. Rahimi, B.; Chua, H.T. Low grade heat driven multi-effect distillation and desalination. *Low Grade Heat Driven Multi-Effect Distill. Desalin.* **2017**, *54*, 1–194.
204. Lara, J.R.; Osunsan, O.; Holtzapple, M.T. Advanced Mechanical Vapor-Compression Desalination System. *Desalination Trends Technol.* **2011**, *7*, 129–148. [[CrossRef](#)]
205. Wayman, J. *Philip Davies Brackish Ground Water Desalination Using Solar Reverse Osmosis*; School of Engineering and Applied Science, Aston University: Birmingham, UK, 2015.
206. Baniasad Askari, I.; Ameri, M. A techno-economic review of multi effect desalination systems integrated with different solar thermal sources. *Appl. Therm. Eng.* **2021**, *185*, 116323. [[CrossRef](#)]
207. Toth, A.J. Modelling and optimisation of multi-stage flash distillation and reverse osmosis for desalination of saline process wastewater sources. *Membranes* **2020**, *10*, 265. [[CrossRef](#)]
208. Nannarone, A.; Toro, C.; Sciubba, E. Multi-stage flash desalination process: Modeling and simulation. In Proceedings of the The 30th International Conference on Efficiency, Cost, Optimization, Simulation and Environmental Impact of Energy Systems-ECOS 2017, San Diego, CA, USA, 2–6 July 2017.
209. Khoshrou, I.; Jafari Nasr, M.R.; Bakhtari, K. New opportunities in mass and energy consumption of the Multi-Stage Flash Distillation type of brackish water desalination process. *Sol. Energy* **2017**, *153*, 115–125. [[CrossRef](#)]
210. El-Ghonemy, A.M.K. Performance test of a sea water multi-stage flash distillation plant: Case study. *Alexandria Eng. J.* **2018**, *57*, 2401–2413. [[CrossRef](#)]
211. Baig, H.; Antar, M.A.; Zubair, S.M. Performance evaluation of a once-through multi-stage flash distillation system: Impact of brine heater fouling. *Energy Convers. Manag.* **2011**, *52*, 1414–1425. [[CrossRef](#)]
212. Fera-Díaz, J.J.; López-Méndez, M.C.; Rodríguez-Miranda, J.P.; Sandoval-Herazo, L.C.; Correa-Mahecha, F. Commercial thermal technologies for desalination of water from renewable energies: A state of the art review. *Processes* **2021**, *9*, 262. [[CrossRef](#)]
213. González, D.; Amigo, J.; Suárez, F. Membrane distillation: Perspectives for sustainable and improved desalination. *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* **2017**, *80*, 238–259. [[CrossRef](#)]
214. Reza Shirzad Kebria, M.; Rahimpour, A. Membrane Distillation: Basics, Advances, and Applications. In *Advances in Membrane Technologies*; IntechOpen: London, UK, 2020. [[CrossRef](#)]
215. Bendevis, P.; Karam, A.; Laleg-Kirati, T.M. Optimal model-free control of solar thermal membrane distillation system. *Comput. Chem. Eng.* **2020**, *133*, 106622. [[CrossRef](#)]
216. Chang, H.; Chang, C.L.; Hung, C.Y.; Cheng, T.W.; Ho, C.D. Optimization Study of Small-Scale Solar Membrane Distillation Desalination Systems (s-SMDDS). *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health* **2014**, *11*, 12064–12087. [[CrossRef](#)]
217. Muhamad, N.A.S.; Hanoin, M.A.H.M.; Mokhtar, N.M.; Lau, W.J.; Jaafar, J. Industrial application of membrane distillation technology using palm oil mill effluent in Malaysia. *Mater. Today Proc.* **2021**, *57*, 1282–1287. [[CrossRef](#)]
218. Lu, K.; Lü, Y.; Bai, Y.; Zhang, J.; Bie, N.; Ren, Y.; Ma, Y. Experimental investigation and theoretical modeling on scale behaviors of high salinity wastewater in zero liquid discharge process of coal chemical industry. *Chinese J. Chem. Eng.* **2020**, *28*, 969–979. [[CrossRef](#)]
219. Xiong, R.; Wei, C. Current status and technology trends of zero liquid discharge at coal chemical industry in China. *J. Water Process. Eng.* **2017**, *19*, 346–351. [[CrossRef](#)]
220. Alnouri, S.Y.; Linke, P.; El-Halwagi, M.M. Accounting for central and distributed zero liquid discharge options in interplant water network design. *J. Clean. Prod.* **2018**, *171*, 644–661. [[CrossRef](#)]
221. Deneux, O.; El Hafni, B.; Péchiné, B.; Di Penta, E.; Antonucci, G.; Nuccio, P. Establishment of a model for a combined heat and power plant with ThermosysPro library. *Procedia Comput. Sci.* **2013**, *19*, 746–753. [[CrossRef](#)]
222. Hernandez-Albaladejo, G.; Urquia, A. Modelling of Low-Temperature Solar Thermal Systems with Modelica. *IFAC-PapersOnLine* **2018**, *51*, 783–788. [[CrossRef](#)]
223. Halimov, A.; Lauster, M.; Müller, D. Validation and integration of a latent heat storage model into building envelopes of a high-order building model for Modelica library AixLib. *Energy Build.* **2019**, *202*, 109336. [[CrossRef](#)]
224. Xanthopoulou, K.; Mehrfeld, P.; Kangowski, P.; Lanzerath, F.; Müller, D. Validation of a building model as part of the AixLib Modelica library for dynamic plant and building performance simulations. *Energy Build.* **2021**, *250*, 111248. [[CrossRef](#)]
225. Filonenko, K.; Ljungdahl, V.B.; Yang, T.; Veje, C. Modelica implementation of phase change material ventilation unit. In Proceedings of the 2020 6th IEEE International Energy Conference (ENERGYCon), Gammarth, Tunisia, 28 September–1 October 2020; pp. 464–467. [[CrossRef](#)]
226. Aguilera, M.; Vanfretti, L.; Bogodorova, T.; Gómez, F. Coalesced Gas Turbine and Power System Modeling and Simulation using Modelica. In Proceedings of the American Modelica Conference 2018, Somberg Conference Center, Cambridge, MA, USA, 9–10 October 2019; Volume 154, pp. 93–102. [[CrossRef](#)]

227. Desideri, A.; Hernandez, A.; Gusev, S.; van den Broek, M.; Lemort, V.; Quoilin, S. Steady-state and dynamic validation of a small-scale waste heat recovery system using the ThermoCycle Modelica library. *Energy* **2016**, *115*, 684–696. [CrossRef]
228. Antoniadis, C.N.; Martinopoulos, G. Simulation of Solar Thermal Systems with Seasonal Storage Operation for Residential Scale Applications. *Procedia Environ. Sci.* **2017**, *38*, 405–412. [CrossRef]
229. Ekwonu, M.C.; Perry, S.; Oyedoh, E.A. Modelling and Simulation of Gas Engines Using Aspen HYSYS. Available online: <https://www.aspentech.com/en/products/engineering/aspen-hysys> (accessed on 10 June 2022).
230. Benato, A.; Stoppato, A.; Mirandola, A.; Del Medico, M. Design and Off-Design Analysis of an ORC Coupled with a Micro-Gas Turbine. *Energy Procedia* **2017**, *129*, 551–558. [CrossRef]
231. Zheng, L.; Furimsky, E. ASPEN simulation of cogeneration plants. *Energy Convers. Manag.* **2003**, *44*, 1845–1851. [CrossRef]
232. Alobaid, F.; Postler, R.; Ströhle, J.; Epple, B.; Kim, H.G. Modeling and investigation start-up procedures of a combined cycle power plant. *Appl. Energy* **2008**, *85*, 1173–1189. [CrossRef]
233. Antonelli, M.; Baccioli, A.; Francesconi, M.; Psaroudakis, P.; Martorano, L. Small scale ORC plant modeling with the AMESim simulation tool: Analysis of working fluid and thermodynamic cycle parameters influence. *Energy Procedia* **2015**, *81*, 440–449. [CrossRef]
234. Ramin Moradi; Roberto Tascioni; Emanuele Habib; Luca Cioccolanti; Mauro Villarini; Enrico Bocci Thermodynamic simulation of a small-scale organic Rankine cycle testing facility using R245fa. *Energy Procedia* **2018**, *148*, 66–73. [CrossRef]
235. Borelli, D.; Devia, F.; Schenone, C.; Spoladore, A. Thermodynamic transient simulation of a combined heat & power system. *Energy Procedia* **2015**, *81*, 505–515. [CrossRef]
236. Joe, J.M.; Rabiou, A.M. Retrofit of the Heat Recovery System of a Petroleum Refinery Using Pinch Analysis. *J. Power Energy Eng.* **2013**, *01*, 47–52. [CrossRef]
237. Cassanello, M.; Yeoh, K.P.; Liang, Y.; Pamudji, M.S.; Hui, C.W. Modelling and optimization of multistream heat exchanger with area targeting. *Chem. Eng. Trans.* **2018**, *70*, 673–678. [CrossRef]
238. Biyanto, T.R.; Tama, N.E.; Permatasari, I.; Sabillah, M.G.; Napitupulu, D.H.; Anda, A.R. Optimization heat transfer coefficient in retrofit heat exchanger network using pinch analysis and killer whale algorithm. *AIP Conf. Proc.* **2019**, *2088*, 020051. [CrossRef]
239. Bagajewicz, M.; Roderer, H.; Savelski, M. Energy efficient water utilization systems in process plants. *Comput. Chem. Eng.* **2002**, *26*, 59–79. [CrossRef]
240. Ganjeh Kaviri, A.; Mohd Jafar, M.N.; Tholudin, M.L. Modeling and optimization of Heat Recovery Heat exchanger. *Appl. Mech. Mater.* **2012**, *110–116*, 2448–2452. [CrossRef]
241. Yang, M.H. Optimizations of the waste heat recovery system for a large marine diesel engine based on transcritical Rankine cycle. *Energy* **2016**, *113*, 1109–1124. [CrossRef]
242. Li, D.; Sun, Q.; Sun, K.; Zhang, G.; Bai, S.; Li, G. Diesel engine waste heat recovery system comprehensive optimization based on system and heat exchanger simulation. *Open Phys.* **2021**, *19*, 331–340. [CrossRef]
243. Tanasic, N.; Ivosevic, M.; Simonovic, T. Optimisation of waste heat recovery system in paper machine dryer section. In Proceedings of the 2021 6th International Symposium on Environment-Friendly Energies and Applications (EFEA), Sofia, Bulgaria, 24–26 March 2021. [CrossRef]
244. Wang, X.; Jin, M.; Feng, W.; Shu, G.; Tian, H.; Liang, Y. Cascade energy optimization for waste heat recovery in distributed energy systems. *Appl. Energy* **2018**, *230*, 679–695. [CrossRef]
245. Castelli, A.F.; Elsidio, C.; Scaccabarozzi, R.; Nord, L.O.; Martelli, E. Optimization of organic rankine cycles for waste heat recovery from aluminum production plants. *Front. Energy Res.* **2019**, *7*, 44. [CrossRef]
246. Laouid, Y.A.A.; Kezrane, C.; Lasbet, Y.; Pesyridis, A. Towards improvement of waste heat recovery systems: A multi-objective optimization of different organic Rankine cycle configurations. *Int. J. Thermofluids* **2021**, *11*, 100100. [CrossRef]
247. Legorburu, G.; Smith, A.D. Demonstrating the benefit of multi-objective optimization and clustering for the design of waste heat recovery systems. *ASHRAE Trans.* **2019**, *125*, 436–443.
248. Sani, M.M.; Noorpoor, A.; Motlagh, M.S. Multi objective optimization of waste heat recovery in cement industry (a case study). *J. Therm. Eng.* **2020**, *6*, 604–618. [CrossRef]
249. Valencia, G.; Núñez, J.; Duarte, J. Multiobjective optimization of a plate heat exchanger in a waste heat recovery organic rankine cycle system for natural gas engines. *Entropy* **2019**, *21*, 655. [CrossRef] [PubMed]
250. Feru, E.; Goyal, S.; Willems, F. Optimal Sizing of Waste Heat Recovery Systems for Dynamic Engine Conditions. In *Organic Rankine Cycle Technology for Heat Recovery*; IntechOpen: London, UK, 2018. [CrossRef]
251. Powell, K.M.; Hedengren, J.D.; Edgar, T.F. Dynamic optimization of a solar thermal energy storage system over a 24 hour period using weather forecasts. In Proceedings of the 2013 American Control Conference, Washington, DC, USA, 17–19 June 2013; pp. 2946–2951. [CrossRef]
252. Li, J.; Zhang, Y.; Ding, P.; Long, E. Experimental and simulated optimization study on dynamic heat discharge performance of multi-units water tank with PCM. *Indoor Built Environ.* **2021**, *30*, 1531–1545. [CrossRef]
253. Hoffmann, C.; Puta, H. Dynamic optimization of energy supply systems with Modelica models. *IFAC Proc. Vol.* **2006**, *1*, 51–56. [CrossRef]
254. Zhang, L.; Wang, Y.; Feng, X. A framework for design and operation optimization for utilizing low-grade industrial waste heat in district heating and cooling. *Energies* **2021**, *14*, 2190. [CrossRef]

-
255. Marton, S.; Langner, C.; Svensson, E.; Harvey, S. Costs vs. Flexibility of Process Heat Recovery Solutions Considering Short-Term Process Variability and Uncertain Long-Term Development. *Front. Chem. Eng.* **2021**, *3*, 25. [[CrossRef](#)]
 256. Benvenuto, G.; Trucco, A.; Campora, U. Optimization of waste heat recovery from the exhaust gas of marine diesel engines. *Proc. Inst. Mech. Eng. Part M J. Eng. Marit. Environ.* **2016**, *230*, 83–94. [[CrossRef](#)]
 257. Prun, O.E.; Garyaev, A.B. Method for Optimization of Heat-Exchange Units Working in Heat Recovery Systems. *Therm. Eng.* **2020**, *67*, 560–566. [[CrossRef](#)]